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Beyond the Classroom: Exploring Teacher Agency in Making and Breaking Educational Reforms

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Abstract

Vocational education and training (VET) teachers are at the forefront of educational reforms aimed at shifting learning from school to company environments, also known as dual VET reforms. Yet little is known about their agency in this process. This article thus investigates the agency of schoolteachers impacted by the introduction of dual VET reforms in post-socialist, school-based VET systems. Interview transcripts conducted with VET school teachers, school directors, and VET experts in Albania and Slovakia provide data for the qualitative content analysis. The findings reveal that teacher agency is characterised by a multi-objective optimisation process between teachers' absolute numbers of reimbursed working hours, their professional status and learner's well-being. When navigating their agency through insecure educational reforms embedded within distinct structural and institutional pressures, teachers rely on their experience to estimate what coping strategy to adopt. They either block the introduction of dual VET reforms to maintain the status quo or embrace them as an opportunity to realise their material and professional interests. These insights are key when designing policy and capacity-increasing measure to ensure the buy-in of micro-level gatekeepers in educational reforms.

Keywords

vocational teachers, dual system, educational and training reform, reform, politics of education, transition economy

1 Introduction

Educational change processes are multi-directional, multi-layered, and fragile (Ball, 2006; Schulte, 2018). They depend on the continuous political support of all involved actors and stakeholders (Busemeyer & Trampusch, 2012). Extensive research has focussed on macro-, meso-, and micro-political level actors in explaining the outcome of educational reforms, including incumbent decision-makers and political parties, education bureaucrats, teacher unions, donor and international organisations, and employers as the “consumers” of the education sector (Ansell, 2010; Bruns et al., 2019; Fichtner, 2010; Moe & Wiborg, 2016). However, one underestimated policy-maker – rather than commonly considered policy-taker – in education reforms are schools, specifically schoolteachers (Grindle, 2004).

Despite being critical actors in implementing and translating education reforms, their agency has not received adequate attention. Drawing on Emirbayer and Mische's (1998) perspective, teacher agency is understood as teachers' motivation and creativity that allow them to overcome structural constraints. This refers to a temporally limited process, where teachers choose among different options, make judgements that are informed by the past but also oriented towards the future, and act upon their choices. Then as street-level bureaucrats, teachers can initiate, influence and resist school-level implementation of reforms through blocking and interpreting policy as they see fit (Ball et al., 2012; Lipsky, 1980). Teacher agency studies argue that teacher agency is shaped by various factors like the ecological environment in which they are embedded in, their professional identity, efficacy beliefs, or political interference from teachers' unions (Giudici, 2021; Mizala & Schneider, 2014; Priestley et al., 2015a; Pyhältö et al., 2015). These insights however mainly derive from studies investigating teachers in primary and general education tracks in advanced capitalist democracies. Surprisingly little is known about the teacher agency in vocational education and training (VET) tracks and in contexts where their interests are weakly organised via teacher unions.

The lack of focus on the agency of VET teachers is puzzling since they are the number one educational actors coming under immense pressure due to the rise of reforms aiming to shift vocational learning and teaching in schools to work-based learning in company environments (ADB, 2009; Cedefop & OECD, 2021; European Commission, 2017; Li & Pilz, 2021). Moreover, VET teachers are a unique category of teachers because of their "dual professional identity" from being teachers in upper secondary vocational programmes and being skilled workers in an occupational trade (Sandal, 2021). As a result, many VET teachers consider their role as "proponents of the vocational" (Heikkinen, 1997, p. 215). This paper thus asks: What is the agency of VET teachers? What coping and optimisation strategies do they adopt to deal with structural constraints and pressures they are embedded in?

From a theoretical perspective, the paper speaks to recent approaches that aim to theorise how political processes at the micro-level shape macro-politics and institutional change in education systems. From a practical perspective, the findings shed light on the determinants and drivers of agency within VET schools. This is key for understanding the dynamics underlying educational change or the lack thereof, and thus for formulating policy recommendations to minimise the mismatch between official reforms and the actual practices of VET.

2 Teacher agency

There is a long history of teachers initiating, influencing, and resisting education policies (Giudici, 2021; Moe, 2016). A broad literature strand investigates teacher agency, usually exercised by teacher unions, within macro-political policy generation phases, such as formulating official legislative texts that regulate formal education (Bowe et al., 1992; Liebermann, 1997; Moe & Wiborg, 2016). The policy generation phase (e.g., legislative breakthroughs) is irrelevant to this paper. Instead, teachers are studied as individual front-line workers that engage with education policies on the ground. A range of studies on teacher agency focus on the psychological, technological, pedagogical, ethnographic, professional identity and practice, or "day-to-day adult-adult relationships" dimensions of teacher agency (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009; Eteläpelto et al., 2014; Isopahkala-Bouret, 2010; Molla & Nolan, 2020; Priestley et al., 2015b; Tyler & Dymock, 2021). However, to understand teachers as "institutional entrepreneur" able to create new, reshape or defend existing practices and institutions (Battilana et al., 2009; DiMaggio, 1988), a political-economic lens needs to be adopted. This lens considers the entire structure-, institution- and interest-based dimensions of teacher agency.

This extensive analytical level encompasses the interactions and relationships between actors, negotiations, collaboration, conflict, the distributions of resources, and formal and informal power (Ball et al., 2012). Together, they determine how education policies are interpreted, translated, and implemented – and the according educational institutions are stabilised or challenged for change to happen. Although teachers dispose of relatively high degrees of discretion, autonomy, and hidden agendas, their interests and preferences are still embedded and constructed by institutions and structures (Datnow, 2020; Priestley et al., 2015a). Thus, to identify and understand teacher agency, we need to situate teachers' agency in a dynamic relationship within the respective structures and institutions (Battilana et al., 2009). Therefore, in a first step, we need to identify the structural and institutional features that are significant for VET school teachers. Structures cannot be changed in the mid-term, but institutions can because as informal and formal “rules of the game” (e.g., regulations and practices that shape the VET system) they mediate the relation between structure and agency (Giddens, 1984). In a second step, taking structure and institutions into account, we can then incorporate key analytical concepts from the political-economic literature strands to understand teacher agency, such as commitment problems, collective actions problems, and information asymmetries.

3 Research design

I explore the agency of VET school teachers faced with the introduction of dual VET reforms in post-communist countries these factors collectively provide a critical case to explore teachers' agency and their coping and adaptation strategies (Gerring, 2007). Firstly, post-communist countries feature nearly exclusively state-driven and school-based VET systems since state-owned enterprises were privatised and retreated from participating in VET after the fall of communist regimes in the early 1990s (Tütlys et al., 2022). Secondly, meso-level actors like teacher unions are generally weakly politicised in post-socialist contexts (Baboš, 2010; Schoenman, 2014), allowing to better identify and conceptualise VET school teachers' agency without interfering forces from organised interests.

Thirdly and most importantly, several governments in former communist countries launched educational reforms inspired by the dual VET model within policy diffusion initiatives driven by supranational or donor organisations (Cedefop, 2020; Galvin Arribas & Papadakis, 2019). A key feature of the dual VET model is that learners, mostly at upper secondary education level, acquire general and occupation specific skills during school- and company-based learning phases (Gonon, 2014). This institutional arrangement of organising VET is considered beneficial for reaching the double objective of adjusting the VET system to the productive sector and improving youth unemployment. However, shifting an exclusively state-driven and school-based VET system towards a system characterised by strong private sector engagement is extremely difficult due to sticky path dependencies and collective action problems. The buy-in of employers and students is undeniably a necessary precondition for dual VET reforms to succeed and are therefore widely studied (Amesti et al., 2021; Bolli et al., 2021; Chankseliani & Anuar, 2019; James Relly & Laczik, 2022; Mora et al., 2022; Wołodźko et al., 2021). But teachers in VET schools, specifically practical instructors who teach practical learning lessons, are the number one actor at risk losing the most from dual VET reforms: their jobs. The reason is that truly implementing reforms inspired by the dual VET system essentially means shifting learning provided by teachers within schools' environments to learning provided by employees in company premises. Given these pressures, VET teachers are very likely actors to develop agency when faced with the introduction of dual VET reforms.

To explore teacher agency, the empirical analysis investigates the transcripts of semi-structured interviews transcripts conducted with ten schoolteachers employed in eight different VET schools in Albania and Slovakia (see Annex). The data were collected in the framework

of a larger research project investigating the participation of companies in VET, but had a specific interview section dedicated to teachers' role in implementing practices inspired by the dual VET model. Secondary and grey literature and transcripts from thirteen further interviews with VET school directors, VET experts and public authorities designing and implementing VET reforms were additionally consulted for triangulation purposes. Data were analysed thematically using a deductive, yet flexible coding approach (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). This approach implied starting with a preconceived set of codes to analyse the interview transcripts but adding new and unexpected themes that emerged during the coding process. The selection of Albania and Slovakia allows drawing generalisations about teacher agency in post-socialist contexts with greater confidence. The two countries differ along important background factors (levels of economic development, advancement of political-economic institutions, significance of the VET system). However, they are similar with regards to the recent introduction of reforms and legislation inspired by the dual VET model (introduction of the "Law 15/2017 on VET" in Albania and the "Act n. 61/2015 on VET" in Slovakia).

4 Findings

4.1 Structural and institutional context

To understand the agency of VET teachers, first, a structural and institutional context analysis was undertaken to understand the context in which teachers are embedded in. In the case of implementing dual VET reforms, structurally, we find that demographic factors, historical legacies from the communist area, and rapid technological changes contribute to an environment in which VET school teachers find themselves in a disenfranchised position.

Firstly, with the decline of large state-owned enterprises and a strong prioritisation of the general education tracks in the 1990s in both countries, many VET schools in the 1990s became redundant (Gordon & Bartlett, 2016). Public authorities feared a loss of public land if former VET school buildings were to be privatised. They resisted these pressures, resulting in several post-communist VET systems being marked by many small VET schools distributed across both countries that have small numbers of students and class sizes and relatively high numbers of different VET programmes – contributing to relatively high and inefficient numbers of teachers (ALB2; ALB9; Vantuch & Jelínková, 2022). Particularly in Slovakia, respondents report that there are strong voices demanding a decrease in the numbers of VET schools and an increased efficiency of school management in terms of the ratio of student numbers, VET programmes offered, and teachers per school (SK2; SK3).

Secondly, private sector actors, such as businesses and business interest organisations, exert a high degree of distrust towards the public sector and in particular the education sector. This distrust can be attributed to cultural and historical legacies, such as a general shift from the public to the private sphere, like family, friends, and neighbours, which came about with the breakdown of the socialist system (Letki, 2018). It can also be attributed to a high persistence of corruption, nepotism, and inefficiency in the education system that continue to reinforce distrusting behaviour towards the education system (Cerna, 2014; Zhllima et al., 2018), as this quote by a school director describes: "So seven to eight years ago, it was really difficult to have a high number of students taken to these businesses because the companies were very sceptical about our school, not only about our school but all the schools in general. They wouldn't even try to approach the school and try. [...] It was not an issue of the school itself, it's an issue of the whole system when it comes to these [dual VET] partnerships" (ALB8). Consequently, only a weak trust structure exists preventing a straightforward resolution of collective action problems and the establishment of public-private cooperative behaviour.

Next to these structural factors that originate in historical legacies, demographic factors interact with teachers' agency. Both countries are experiencing rising life expectancy and declining fertility rates, leading to a rapid ageing of their population and some of the fastest declines in working-age populations (OECD, 2022). These tendencies are further accelerated in Albania, which witnessed a first big wave of emigration after the end of communism and a second big wave since the mid-2010s (Gëdeshi & King, 2018; Mara & Landesmann, 2022). In both countries, all respondents made some reference to these demographic changes, which are dramatically decreasing the youth population. These developments put a lot of pressure on VET schools' survival ability since school depend on per capita financing to cover their costs (energy, teacher salaries, maintenance, equipment, etc.). This statement by a teacher exemplifies these pressures:

“We are very impacted by this [demographic change]. The competition between VET schools is too big. A change of the system is needed because it is not made for that. It now depends on the number of students. We have like six VET school in this region plus gymnasium and we have 40'000 inhabitants, that's too much...” (SK7)

Lastly, technological change interacts with VET school teachers' agency: On the one hand by intensifying the preferences of students and their parents to choose general academic tracks that appear to yield higher returns, and on the other hand, by weakening the linkage between VET teachers' knowledge of industrial technologies and the state-of-the-art technologies of production (ALB1; SK3; SK8).

In addition to structural factors, the institutional environment, specifically the legislation, norms, and rules that govern VET, further interact with teachers' agency. While dual VET reforms are accompanied by substantive legislative changes (e.g., the establishment of social dialogue councils and new financing mechanisms), the main change impacting teachers' day-to-day work is that the organisation of work-based learning on the ground is delegated to VET schools (Cedefop, 2020; Hilpert, 2020). This organisation stands in contrast to traditional dual VET systems, where organised business interests like chambers of commerce and associations take over this coordinative role (Emmenegger & Seitzl, 2020). In Albania and Slovakia, teachers and school directors are therefore the main decision-makers at the local level in charge of organising the provision of work-based learning. This includes identifying and reaching out to potential training companies, matching students with companies, assuring the signing of tripartite training contracts (signed between the school, the training company, and the students' parents), creating networks with employers, informing and monitoring training firms during the company-based training phases, and assuring the quality of VET.

Overall, historical legacies and their resulting path dependencies (i.e., large numbers of small VET schools, widespread distrust of the education system, and the weak image of the VET track), as well as demographic, technological and regulatory change shape and embed VET teachers' position within the education system. The structural constraints suggest that they are in a financially and professionally weakened position. At the same time, the changed institutional elements direct towards increased professional demands and a substantial increase in expectations of their professional role.

4.2 Dual VET as an opportunity to realise teacher agency

Faced with the uncertainties accompanying the introduction of dual VET reforms in this specific post-socialist structural and institutional environment, the analysis reveals that teachers seek to optimise three objectives: their paid workload, their professional status, and learners' well-being. They pursue approaches to at the least safeguard their number of working hours, which can include maintaining their teaching lessons but can also consist of substituting teaching with coordinative tasks to secure their work in the short- to mid-term. Secondly, given their “dual professional identity”, they strive to being recognised as a pedagogical or

occupational expert by students, parents, and companies. Lastly, they consider their student's well-being in this process, which includes protecting students' interests in the world of work.

To realise their agency, teachers adopt and act upon two different strategies. One strategy of teachers is to resist the introduction of dual VET reforms and their according elements and practices by not organising work-based learning phases in company premises. Their underlying logic can be explained by fears that the shift to company-based learning will decrease their working hours, or – the opposite – undermine their right to adequate compensation despite increased workload in organising company-based learning, and thereby further erode their professional standing. For example, in Slovakia the introduction of dual VET first led to massive teacher resistance towards dual VET reforms because the headcount funding was decreased due to the shift of learning taking place in company premises (Vantuch & Jelínková, 2020). This statement highlights the issue: “The problem at the beginning was that if the school signed dual education with the company, their money for the kids were reduced by like 50%, because it was normal that if the students are within the company, 50% of the time, you will receive less money, and the school started to resist that because if I have less money, why should I support that?” (SK3). In Albania, a middle-income country with very low education spending, the increase in workload to coordinate work-based learning with training firms also conflicts with material interests: “If you don't get paid for what you are doing, of course people oppose it.” (ALB7).

Professionally, it can be found that especially mid-career level teachers with around 20 years of teaching experience are most likely actors to resist dual VET reforms. They are not familiar with the advantages of work-based learning, are sceptical of private sector actors' ability to train the skills and competencies foreseen in the curricula, and are concerned that VET students are principally used as cheap labour. They believe that all occupational skills can be acquired in a school environment. Given the weak monitoring and enforcement capacities of reforms by superior actors (e.g., ministries of education and regional education authorities), they have much leeway to resist reforms. This strategy choice is likely attributed to their own negative experience with the world of work, especially not finding adequate or safe employment as a skilled worker during the transition years and then opting for publicly financed and secure teacher position. By considering the past, they choose to maintain the status quo as the most secure strategy to safeguard their material and professional interests and realise their agency.

In contrast, equally driven by material and professional motivations, some teachers adopted an entirely different approach. Instead of resisting the shift to company-based learning, they took the risk and creatively embraced dual VET reforms as a window of opportunity to secure future working hours, student enrolments and VET schools' survival. Considering the past, present, and future structural constraints, VET school teachers utilise dual VET reforms as an opportunity to maintain or even increase the demand for VET and according number of student enrolments, observing that shifting some learning to companies makes the school popular “like a magnet” (ALB3). The teachers who took the risk of engaging with companies realised that potential fears of losing jobs didn't materialise but secured and expanded their workload since new classes were needed. Some also pursued adaptation strategies between maintaining the status quo and embracing dual VET. This entails optimising the number of students that VET teachers send to training companies and those kept in school-based workshops to ensure that VET school teachers can maintain their teaching hours.

Next to material motives reflected in instrumentalising dual VET as a strategy to increase numbers of students, professional motives are also visible. The transformation of practical learning teachers to formal or informal business relationship coordinators appears to be strategy to substitute the potential loss of practical teaching hours in the schools. This role entails a diverse set of tasks such as conducting research on local companies, organising school visits

for companies, providing information on the content of curricula, matching students with companies, promoting the VET track, setting up training contracts, and accompanying, coordinating, and monitoring the learning phases. This substitution of tasks enriches their professional profile content-wise and in terms of workload. Vis-à-vis parents and local companies, it also strengthens and transforms their role towards being experts on pedagogy and learning. Given that post-communist contexts are marked by strong localised communities and a relatively low image of the VET track, engaging professionally with locally respected companies, and successfully integrating local youth in the labour market can increase the teachers' credibility, legitimacy, and prestige.

It can be observed that pre-dominantly early-career and in the case of Slovakia also late-career teachers are the likely actors pursuing the strategy of optimising dual VET to their advantage. In Slovakia, older teachers are familiar with the VET system that existed during socialist times, which was characterised by a strong cooperation between large state-owned enterprises and local VET schools. The impact of the transition on the Slovak VET system was less extreme than on the Albanian VET system. Thus, many teachers in Slovakia with over thirty years of teaching experience report a greater understanding and sympathy of the idea behind reforms inspired by the dual VET system, especially of the advantages of work-based learning phases since many of them also gained mandatory industry experience during socialist times. This is different in Albania, which experienced a highly repressive communist regime, and where teachers were known to be "so strict and rigid, and just want to teach what is in the book" (ALB3). These types of teachers rarely survived the transition period since the Albanian VET track nearly completely eroded, leading to a more significant number of relatively younger teachers compared to the Slovak VET system.

4.3 Conditions to realise teacher agency

Two conditions need to be in place for schoolteachers to be able to realise their agency. Firstly, school directors are the central authority in school environments that can support or block the agency of schoolteachers. Equally driven by financial and professional motivations, some school directors resist the shift of learning to company premises. They oppose the additional responsibility and risks arising from students being taught in company premises or fear that the increased cooperation between VET teachers and companies will lead to a loss of their power and professional standing. This quote exemplifies the opposition:

"So therefore, in some parts of Slovakia, the cooperation worked, even before legislative introduction of dual VET [...]. Schools, in case there is a clever director, they are very effective in cooperation. In case there is an idiot, then they are not interested because from economical point of view, the quality doesn't matter for the directors. And so for them, it is much better to not to have a complication. Shifting some work to the company, being responsible if something happens in the company, I will have a problem as a director. So I will push them into my school workshop, and that's fine. You know, money is in my house. No problem." (SK1)

However, some directors, like VET teachers, approach dual VET practices as an opportunity to increase student enrolments and their headcount financing, improve their professional reputation, and secure their political survival. Since school directors are usually appointed by local political authorities or ministry officials, they can increase their credibility and political leverage if they have strong backing by the local private sector, who show interest in the students they educate. Lastly, given that dual VET is high on international and national policy agendas, adopting practices of dual VET is also a potential strategy to access additional financial assistance (e.g., donor or European funding).

Secondly, instituting elements inspired by the dual VET requires cooperation between actors with diverging interests (Busemeyer & Trampusch, 2012). The analysis of the structural

and institutional context that shapes teacher agency already indicated major collective action problems (e.g., weak trust in the education sector, a weak image of the VET system, lack of information about the content of VET programs, weak enforcement measures, weak organisation of businesses' and teachers' interests). They restrict the development of practices inspired by the dual VET model. How can the teachers, who perceive dual VET as a strategy to realise professional and financial motivation, overcome these collective action problems and enforce the commitments of training companies – the fundamental actor needed to realise their agency? The analysis revealed that establishing and nurturing of trust-based relationships with companies is the critical ingredient for cooperation to arise in such low-trust-low-coordination environments. They continuously cultivate trust with companies via regular interactions, face-to-face communication, deliberation, and individualised support to training firms to overcome commitment problems and build local trust networks to make cooperation work. With the establishment of trust-based relationships, the teachers also feel comfortable and confident to flexibly adapt the learning plans according to the needs of the companies and state-of-the-art technologies, and to delegate their know-how monopoly to company instructors.

Altogether, building on trust-based relationships and shifting learning to the company environment in turn can also interact with and shape the structural and institutional constraints. VET schools that support and maintain the shift to company-based learning report that their school was perceived as more attractive by key stakeholders (parents, political actors, the private sector), to increase the VET school track's reputation, to improve the quality of learning and employment prospects for students, and altogether secure the VET track's survival.

5 Conclusion and policy recommendations

Identifying pathways for change in education system requires a thorough understanding of the structures and institutions that shape the agency of vital stakeholders, especially teachers. The analysis of teachers' agency in post-socialist countries indicates that teachers impacted by dual VET reforms have far more capacity and substantial interests to block or drive change than might be expected. Suffering from socialist legacies, demographic changes, and a weak reputation of and trust in the VET system, teachers, together with directors, can instrumentalise the cooperation with businesses to secure their material and professional motivations. They can maintain the status quo or compete for enrolments and funding, transform their professional profile, and improve their professional standing. In the context of the two post-socialist countries Albania and Slovakia, these forces are independent of higher levels of teacher unionisation or interest organisation. Teacher buy-in is therefore crucial as it “can have as much impact on reform outcomes as the actual content of the reform” (Grindle, 2004, p. 119).

On the ground, the engagement of teachers and companies and their cooperative relationships are diverse and accompanied by additional challenges in terms of sustainability, efficiency, accountability, and quality assurance. However, these first years of cooperation observed in the Albanian and Slovak VET schools, and the minor changes they provoked for teacher's professional development, the attractiveness of the VET track, and the integration of students into the labour market, can accumulate, leading to breakthroughs at the provision level, and even transforming the underlying structures and institutions shaping the overall VET systems.

Two policy recommendations can be derived from the analysis. Firstly, it is crucial to avoid reducing funding for schools and teachers, which would backfire on the implementation level. Teacher's incomes and careers are directly or indirectly impacted by dual VET reforms. Instead, the loss of teaching hours and professional standing must be substituted or enhanced. One avenue can be the transformation of the role and tasks of teachers to coordinators of business relationships, enriching their job profile and securing enough working hours. This strategy does not only secure their material interests, but also their professional interests. Secondly, it is

essential to strengthen the capacities of teachers to take over this coordinative role so that they can build trust-based relationships with private sector actors. Taking the seniority level and experience of teachers into account, capacity measures should ensure that teachers feel sure in their communication with companies, and can manage company relations, advertise and promote VET programmes, monitor training phases, and build strategies to deal with problems, conflicts, and commitment issues.

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Biographical notes

Linda Wanklin is a scientific researcher (PhD candidate) in the Swiss Leading House GOVPET at the University of St. Gallen.

Annex

Table 1
Interview participants

Nr.	ID	Function	Sector	Location	Date	Length
1	ALB1	Professional expert on work-based learning	Donor organisation	Tirana, Albania	25.10.2021	01:19h
2	ALB2	Director	National state agency in charge of VET	Tirana, Albania (online)	25.10.2021	00:36h
3	ALB3	School director	Public VET school	Lezha, Albania	26.10.2021	01:35h
4	ALB4	Teacher	Public VET school	Lezha, Albania	26.10.2021	00:32h
5	ALB5	Teacher	Public VET school	Shkodra, Albania	27.10.2021	01:12h
6	ALB6	School director	Public VET school	Vlora, Albania	1.11.2021	01:00h
7	ALB7	Teacher	Public VET school	Berat, Albania	2.11.2021	00:40h
8	ALB8	School director	Public VET school	Tirana, Albania	3.11.2021	00:45h
9	ALB9	Professional experts on Albanian VET system	Donor organisation (multinational)	Tirana, Albania	4.11.2021	01:17h
10	ALB10	Professional expert on Albanian VET system	Donor Organisation (Switzerland)	Tirana, Albania	5.11.2021	01:09h
11	ALB11	Teacher	Public VET school	Elbasan, Albania	8.11.2021	00:23h
12	ALB12	Professional expert on Albanian VET system	Donor organisation (Austria)	Vienna, Austria (online)	19.11.2021	01:04h
13	SK1	Academic Expert for VET	University	Bratislava, Slovakia (online)	24.03.2022	01:13h
14	SK2	Professional expert on work-based learning	Umbrella employer organisation in charge of dual VET	Bratislava, Slovakia (online)	24.03.2022	00:42h
15	SK3	Secretary General and Coordinator for dual VET	Agency organisation in charge of dual VET	Bratislava, Slovakia	02.05.2022	01:17h
16	SK4	School director	Public VET school	Bratislava, Slovakia	04.05.2022	01:00h
17	SK5	School director	Public VET school	Bratislava, Slovakia	04.05.2022	00:45h
18	SK6	School director and a teacher	Public VET school	Bratislava, Slovakia	06.05.2022	01:10h
19	SK7	Two teachers	Private VET school	Nitra, Slovakia	11.05.2022	00:50h

20	SK8	Two teachers	Public VET school	Piest'any, Slovakia	12.05.2022	01:15h
21	SK9	School director, teacher, company representative	Public VET school	Trnava, Slovakia	13.05.2022	01:05h
22	SK10	Director	National state agency in charge of VET	Bratislava, Slovakia	18.5.2022	01:10h
23	SK11	Regional coordinator for dual VET	Public sector agency	Zilina, Slovakia (online)	26.5.2022	0:53h